

Fisnik Muça, PhD¹
Xhemail Çupi, PhD²

UDC: 339.54-027.511]:616.98:578.834

**NDIKIMI I COVID-19 NË TREGTINË NDËRKOMBËTARE -
NDIKIMET POLITIKE DHE EKONOMIKE NË EPOKËN E RE TË
GLOBALIZIMIT**

**ВЛИЈАНИЕТО НА КОВИД-19 ВО МЕЃУНАРОДНАТА
ТРГОВИЈА - ПОЛИТИЧКИ И ЕКОНОМСКИ ЕФЕКТИ ВО
НОВАТА ЕРА НА ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИЈАТА**

**THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON INTERNATIONAL TRADE -
POLITICAL AND ECONOMIC EFFECTS IN THE NEW ERA OF
GLOBALIZATION**

ABSTRACT

Throughout history and in the 19th and 20th centuries, humanity and states faced financial crises: The Great Depression and the Financial Crisis of 2008-2009 had an intense impact on rules and principles of trade and actors in international relations. From the end of 2019 until today, countries face the world pandemic known as COVID-19, which has impacted not only human health but also many other aspects internationally. All this led to setting rules and restrictions by the World Health Organization (WHO) regarding the movement of people and trade; in the decline of the volume and value of international trade in goods and services; production reductions by manufacturing

¹ Administrative clerk at Ministry of Justice of the Republic of North Macedonia, 1250 Debar, North Macedonia, fm06974@seeu.edu.mk

² Lecturer at UBT, Prishtina, Kosovo, xhemail.cupi@ubt-uni.net

companies; restriction of transport services; as well as a substantial decline in passenger airlines and air transport companies; limiting even the executive power of states in some cases. This research aims to highlight the impact that the pandemic has had in terms of international trade and the perspective of states' role in establishing rules and principles regarding the international political economy, especially in the new era of globalization, taking as a case study the states of North Macedonia, Albania, and Kosovo.

Keywords: COVID-19; International political economy; Globalization; International relations; State.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization starts with the person, expands with society and the state, and reaches international organizations' level. Nowadays, special attention is paid to international organizations that in some form serve as an international forum where states discuss important topics and as a regulator of various issues that may arise in the world. For example:

- The United Nations is oriented towards maintaining peace and security between states.

- The International Labor Organization aims to protect workers' rights and treat workers equally throughout the world.

- The World Health Organization (WHO) deals with improving health conditions and promoting new treatments, especially in developing countries, and establishing regulations and procedures for the occurrence of a global pandemic, which has emerged, as never before with the spread of the Corona type virus known as COVID-19 that first appeared in China and then affected almost every country in the world.

According to the UN Framework (2020: 3). “the COVID-19 pandemic is far more than a health crisis: it is affecting societies and economies at their core. While the impact of the pandemic will vary from country to country, it will most likely increase poverty and inequalities at a global scale” that according to all calculations of international institutes and organizations, the economic downturn globally and the decline in the volume of international trade, will exceed the numbers of the financial crisis of 2008-2012.

“Despite the low incidence of the virus in certain regions, the impact of the pandemic has been felt across countries, societies, and the

economy. In most places, whereas the incidence of the virus is still prevalent, Governments face the hard choice between public safety and reviving the economy” (UNDP: 2). The pandemic of the century has affected the rise of poverty, the closure of educational institutions, gender inequality, human security, the decline of family incomes and job losses, the reduction of remittances, the reduction of commodity prices, the rise of food insecurity, the dramatic decline of tourism, and reducing travel.

The last wave of globalization began in 1980 and continues to this day, and dilemmas have arisen among scholars on whether a new era of globalization is beginning and which country will be the primary driver of this wave. Many scholars and journalists also talk about a New World Order for the coronavirus era. According to Alan Crawford (2020), “trends that were already discernible pre-Covid-19 have intensified and accelerated. As a fast-rising power, China is growing more assertive and jostling with countries from Canada to Australia. The US, the one superpower that has remained at the top table since Potsdam, is increasingly self-absorbed as the virus rips through its population and economy ahead of November's presidential election”. Expectations that China will be the second-largest economy in the world have been for 2020, but it has been ranked second since 2010. Although the US remains the most extensive economic leader globally, the Coronavirus pandemic has affected the decline and economic stagnation.

Also, a challenge for current US President Joe Biden will be which direction his administration's foreign policies will continue, because his predecessor not only accused China of the virus issue by calling it “China virus,” but has also taken many other steps that are essentially anti-globalization. His statement that “the WHO has failed to implement reforms” and his accusations of “mismanagement” in the COVID-19 crisis, while keeping biased in China's favor, also constitute an anti-globalization move on his part. “The United States has been the WHO's largest contributor so far. According to Trump, US payments are close to \$ 450 million a year. The obligatory contribution for the years 2020 and 2021 amounts to 116 million dollars. China's contribution to this period is only \$ 57 million” (DW, 2020). His statement sparked debate over whether the US would formally leave the WHO due to which US payments to the organization are very high compared to some other countries in the world. So, the main challenges during this pandemic will be the orientation of states towards “themselves” or

globalization processes. Even though many other countries have not followed the WHO recommendations for pandemic management, it has raised the dilemma of a new era of globalization.

This paper will mainly address the effects of COVID-19 on political issues, based entirely on surveys conducted in different countries. Regarding international trade or foreign trade of goods in North Macedonia, Albania, and Kosovo, statistical data were mainly used by the Statistical Agencies of the respective countries. In October 2020, we developed a mathematical model to forecast the decline in the countries' foreign trade mentioned above, the pessimistic and optimistic scenario in terms of foreign trade of goods.

COVID-19 EFFECTS ON POLITICS

The Covid-19 pandemic has had significant political and economic consequences worldwide. This virus has put pressure on governments to react quickly, decisively and carefully, because any extortion or any previous attempt would have implications on the continuation of their power.

One of the research questions that we will elaborate is: How does the treatment of Covid-19 by a government affect its political legitimacy and its chances of being re-elected? And as a result: Are governments politically punished if they fail to respond by force or immediately to a pandemic?

In a series of social media surveys and data analysis experiments in Canada, Merkle et al. (2020) find that the pandemic has been accompanied by greater party consensus and government support. These studies suggest that the COVID-19 crisis has strengthened the democratic status quo. Bol et al. (2020) “rely on an online survey covering 15 Western European countries and show that the blockade led to a higher consensus - the purpose of the vote - on the country holder, trust in government and satisfaction with democracies.” On the other hand, in a working paper focusing on Spain, Amat et al. (2020) “combine some experimental evidence to show that it has caused a strong national prejudice accompanied by higher demands for techno-authoritarian decision-making.”

Economically, too, governments' responses to the pandemic vary considerably across countries. Placed under the dilemma of fragile health or a declining economy, some governments quickly imposed

strict blocking policies to control case numbers (e.g., Australia or Argentina, Kosovo), while others decided for free policies. to reduce the economic damage of the pandemic (e.g., Brazil, Sweden or the US).

Despite political and economic variations, there has been unanimity only in prolongation and early measures against this pandemic. Anti-Covid measures when the number of victims was still small met numerous internal reactions, both from the opposition and the civil sector, as happened in Kosovo. “In the first months of the pandemic, former Prime Minister Kurti fired the Minister of Interior Agim Veliu, of the LDK, for disagreements over the declaration of a state of emergency, which would give to former President Hashim Thaçi, former leader of PDK, much more power. The coalition further deteriorated when the prime minister announced a lockout that Thaci considered unconstitutional. As a result, a group of local activists called for a non-violent protest from balconies and windows to express opposition to the no-confidence motion that would lead the country to constitutional chaos amid a pandemic and an inevitable global economic recession. These reactions of the civil sector came because state blockades drastically reduce the civil liberties of citizens who see their right to travel freely limited to a minimum, but also because these blockades will have dramatic consequences for the economy, in the short and long term” (Molina, 2020).

Based on the views of the researcher Amat (2020), “situation management tends to create significant exchanges between solid measures to contain the transmission of the virus and civil liberties, and this means that COVID-19 has the potential to jeopardize democracies.”

In the dilemma of whether to vote in pandemic times, such as Covid-19 or to postpone elections, the answer may not be definitive. As stated by Prof. Toby James (minsait.com, 2020), a professor of politics and public policy at the University of East Anglia: “Intuitively, we think postponing an election sounds anti-democratic, [...] but in fact, democracy in some ways can be threatened by holding elections these times. “So we cannot forget that elections take years to plan, from logistics to technology and the security of ballots.”

From this, we can conclude that elections can weaken democracy if the result does not represent the voters' voice who would like to participate but decided against it not to be affected or for fear of infection exposure. Recent preliminary results in the US in the election between Trump and Biden confirm that the pandemic could be one of

the causes of the loss. Donald Trump constantly pushed for a rapid reopening of the economy. This insistence on the second wave of the pandemic, to the point that it requires you not even to wear masks, caused him to become infected with the virus, and his campaign was delayed for several days, and this led to a decrease in the percentage in polls and eventually election defeat.

Another liaison discussion is the balance between the collapse of the economy due to the pandemic and extreme government measures to reduce its pandemic. Based on previous studies of public risk, it emphasizes Herrera et al. (2020), “during a pandemic the public cares more about health outcomes and less about economic outcomes. “According to the Herrera study, governments that put more emphasis on health outcomes versus short-term economic outcomes gained political support.” Whereas, according to his other study with other co-authors (2020), only governments that fail to impose strict countermeasures when experiencing an increase in cases see a decline in approval.

COVID-19 EFFECTS ON FOREIGN TRADE

With the pandemic spreading to EU and US countries, experts and economists at the WTO in April had forecasted a scenario for 2020, when a 13% drop in world merchandise trade was expected, which was the optimistic scenario, up to 32 % that was the pessimistic scenario. This forecast for such a considerable decline came from many countries setting a lockdown and imposed restrictive travel measures, especially air travel. Many companies engaged in producing goods decided to reduce their production capacity, which further deepened the trade decline in goods. “World merchandise trade volume decreased by 14.3% in the second quarter of 2020 over the previous quarter, in seasonally adjusted terms. Economies across the globe implemented strict lockdown measures throughout the period to combat the spread of COVID-19, which led to the sharp decline in trade volume” (WTO, 2020). Although there were similarities in the trade decline magnitudes with that of the 2008-2009 financial crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic was very different from an economic point of view. Even though many countries imposed a lockdown and that the pandemic affected almost every economic sector of goods and services, again in June and July, economists at the WTO created the scenario for the decline of global trade that is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. World merchandise trade volume 2000-2021

(https://www.wto.org/english/news_e/pres20_e/pr862_e.htm)

From Figure 1, we can see that the trade volume of goods is projected to fall by 9.2% in 2020, which is a decline less than the forecast of 13% in the optimistic scenario of April.

Two WTO member states, such as North Macedonia and Albania, and Kosovo, which is not part of the WTO, have been affected by the COVID-19 pandemic in their foreign trade accounts. The impact on foreign trade has come from the lockdown of these states at the start of the pandemic, the curfew's establishment, the declaration of a state of emergency, and the state of crisis. Undoubtedly, all these measures and the recommendations that have been taken into account by the WHO have led to a decline in trade in goods in the countries mentioned above.

Table 1. The exports, imports and trade volume of goods in North Macedonia for the period 2019-2020 (State Statistical Office, 2021)

	000 Euro					
	Exports		Imports		TRADE VOLUME	
Period	2019	2020	2019	2020	2019	2020
January	415311	457039	570092	591393	985403	1048432
February	529847	519903	679646	719795	1209493	1239698
March	588889	430782	740655	607578	1329544	1038360
Q1	1534047	1407724	1990393	1918766	3524440	3326490
April	531918	211263	760761	373751	1292679	585014
May	558774	339357	716425	455456	1275199	794813
June	530495	491965	618539	597704	1149034	1089669
Q2	1621187	1042585	2095725	1426911	3716912	2469496
July	564331	518432	748229	717326	1312560	1235758
August	500656	501153	664552	603384	1165208	1104537
September	563958	586647	653245	676133	1217203	1262780
Q3	1628945	1606232	2066026	1996843	3694971	3603075
October	565860	597330	763731	764493	1329591	1361823
November	567439	578691	739091	695168	1306530	1273859
December	504088	545344	781357	792355	1285445	1337699
Q4	1637387	1721365	2284179	2252016	3921566	3973381
TOTAL	6421566	5777906	8436323	7594536	14857889	13372442

What can be noticed from Table 1 is that the export and import of goods has marked a decline in 2020 compared to 2019. This considerable decline can be observed mostly in April 2020, when in North Macedonia, the first cases of COVID-19 infection began to occur, respectively, in March 2020. This decline is related to the government's restrictive measures, especially with the closure of borders and special procedures for the import and export of goods. While in April 2019 the exports of goods were around 532 million euros, in April 2020, the exports of goods are only 211 million euros, a decrease of around 60%. In May 2020 the export account decreased 39% compared to 2019. Imports of goods during April and May 2020, decreased

compared to 2019. While in April 2020 in the account of import of goods we have a decline of 56%, while in May the decline was 43%. Based on the Q1, Q2, and Q3 quarters, in October 2020, we made a forecast for the optimistic and pessimistic scenario for the decline in exports and imports of goods, respectively, for the trade volume, which is presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Optimistic and pessimistic scenarios for the trade volume in North Macedonia for 2020

Based on the mathematical model, we forecasted the pessimistic scenario that the exports of goods would decrease 11.33%, while according to the optimistic scenario, exports would decrease 11.2%. Regarding the import of goods, we forecasted the pessimistic scenario, which would be a decrease of 9.6%, while according to the optimistic scenario, imports would decrease 6.74%. Even in terms of trade volume, we predicted the pessimistic scenario that the trade volume would decline 10.35%, while the optimistic scenario that the decline will be 8.67%. However, based on the fourth-quarter data, we notice that the forecasts we have made have been approximate, but not

between the scenarios presented. Exports and imports of goods for the years 2019-2020 presented in quarters are illustrated in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Exports and imports of goods in North Macedonia for the years 2019-2020

Based on Figure 3, we can say that there is an increase in exports and imports of goods in 2020 during the fourth quarter compared to 2019. While in 2019, the exports of goods in the fourth quarter were 1.6 billion euros, in 2020, it is 1.7 billion. Imports of goods decreased in the fourth quarter, but still led to an increase in trade volume. Regarding the export of goods, in 2020 compared to 2019, there was a decrease of 10%, while in the import of goods, there was a decrease of 11%, which

led to a decrease of 10% in the trade volume of goods in 2020 compared to the previous year.

In Albania, during January and February of 2020, there is an increase in exports of goods compared to 2019, while in March, April, May, and June, we have a decrease. Exports, imports, and trade volume of goods in Albania for the period 2019-2020 are presented in Table 2. **Table 2.** The exports, imports and trade volume of goods in Albania for the period 2019-2020 (Instat, 2020)

Period	billion ALL					
	Exports		Imports		TRADE VOLUME	
	2019	2020	2019	2020	2019	2020
January	22	23	42	42	64	65
February	23	25	50	52	73	77
March	28	18	56	44	84	62
Q1	73	66	148	138	221	204
April	27	15	57	36	84	51
May	28	22	59	45	87	67
June	26	23	53	52	79	75
Q2	81	60	169	133	250	193
July	28	25	60	57	88	82
August	20	19	52	48	72	67
September	25	25	52	52	77	77
Q3	73	69	164	157	237	226
October	27	27	59	59	86	86
November	25	27	53	56	78	83
December	22	23	56	61	78	84
Q4	74	77	168	176	242	253
TOTAL	301	272	649	604	950	876

While in March 2019, the exports of goods were 28 billion ALL (Albanian Lek), in the same month in 2020, this value is 18 billion ALL. In April 2020 compared to 2019, we had a decrease in exports of goods of 44%, while in May 2020, this decrease is only 21.5%. Also,

the import of goods in March and April 2020 has marked a decline compared to 2019. This decline has deepened in April, where compared to 2019, we have a decrease of around 37%. As in North Macedonia, so in Albania, this decline is due to applying restrictive measures regarding the exports and imports of goods due to the spread of the COVID-19 virus. The optimistic and pessimistic scenario of exports, imports and trade volume for 2020 in Albania is illustrated in Figure 4

Fig. 4. Optimistic and pessimistic scenarios for the trade volume in Albania for 2020

Based on the mathematical model that we developed, we forecasted the pessimistic scenario for Albania that the exports of goods would decrease 10.63 %, while according to the optimistic scenario, that would be a decline of 10.5%. Regarding the imports of goods, we forecasted the pessimistic scenario, which would be a decrease of 8.17%, while according to the optimistic scenario, imports would decrease 7.55%. Even in terms of trade volume, we forecasted the pessimistic scenario that the trade volume would decline 8.95%, while the optimistic scenario that the decline will be 8.53%. However, based on the fourth-quarter data, we notice that the forecasts we have made

have been approximate, but not between the scenarios presented. Exports and imports of goods in Albania for the years 2019-2020 presented in quarters are illustrated in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Exports and imports of goods in Albania for the years 2019-2020

Based on Figure 5, we can say that there is an increase in exports and imports of goods in 2020 during the fourth quarter compared to 2019. While in 2019, the exports of goods in the fourth quarter were 74 billion ALL, in 2020, it is 77 billion ALL. Imports of goods also increased in

the fourth quarter, leading to an increase in trade volume. Regarding the exports of goods, in 2020 compared to 2019, there was a decrease of 9.63%, while in the imports of goods, there was a decrease of 6.93%, which led to a decrease of 8.45% in the trade volume of goods in 2020 compared to the previous year.

Unlike North Macedonia and Albania, Kosovo did not have any deep decline in exports accounts in 2020 compared to 2019. Even the first cases of COVID-19 infected occur later than in North Macedonia and Albania, in March, April, and May, exports in Kosovo, except April, increased. Exports, imports, and trade volume of goods in Kosovo for the period 2019-2020 are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. The exports, imports and trade volume of goods in Kosovo for the period 2019-2020 (Kosovo Agency of Statistics, 2020)

Period	000 Euro					
	Exports		Imports		TRADE VOLUME	
	2019	2020	2019	2020	2019	2020
January	23480	28939	190442	221216	213922	250155
February	24050	35933	232701	263392	256751	299325
March	29572	32164	289192	252070	318764	284234
Q1	77102	97036	712335	736678	789437	833714
April	36940	32688	295496	193974	332436	226662
May	31891	38766	321619	239079	353510	277845
June	32115	44627	275202	290804	307317	335431
Q2	100946	116081	892317	723857	993263	839938
July	40464	42636	336878	306377	377342	349013
August	31906	34317	311857	263305	343763	297622
September	38422	41725	295626	287294	334048	329019
Q3	110792	118678	944361	856976	1055153	975654
October	32339	50637	315050	317689	347389	368326
November	35391	45799	297608	305746	332999	351545
December	26920	46727	335271	355976	362191	402703
Q4	94650	143163	947929	979411	1042579	1122574
TOTAL	383490	474958	3496942	3296922	3880432	3771880

While in March 2019 exports of goods amounted to 29.5 million euros, in the same month of 2020, they amounted to 32.1 million euros, which is an increase of 8.7%. The decrease in the exports account of goods was marked in April by 11.5% compared to 2019. In the following months, the exports accounts of goods marked a significant increase. Compared to exports, imports of goods in 2020, compared to 2019, have marked a decline. This may be because neighboring countries such as North Macedonia and Albania and CEFTA member countries had already applied rules and measures following their situation. There have also been restrictions on Germany and China's goods, a large percentage of imports of goods into Kosovo's foreign trade account. If we take as a basis the month of April 2019, then in April 2020, is a decrease in imports of goods by 34.3%. The optimistic and pessimistic scenario of exports, imports and trade volume for 2020 in Kosovo is illustrated in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Optimistic and pessimistic scenarios for the trade volume in Kosovo for 2020

Based on Figure 6, we forecasted the second scenario for Kosovo that the exports of goods would increase 8.63 %, while according to the first scenario, that would be an increase of 11.2%. Regarding the imports of goods, we forecasted the pessimistic scenario, which would be a decrease of 6.6%, while according to the optimistic scenario, imports would decrease 6.5%. Even in terms of trade volume, we forecasted the pessimistic scenario that the trade volume would decline 5.11%, while the optimistic scenario that the decline will be 4.77%. Based on the fourth-quarter data, we notice that the forecasts we have made have not been even approximate and not between the scenarios presented. Exports and imports of goods in Kosovo for the years 2019-2020 presented in quarters are illustrated in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Exports and imports of goods in Kosovo for the years 2019-2020

Based on Figure 7, we can say that there is an increase in exports and imports of goods in 2020 during the fourth quarter compared to 2019. While in 2019, the exports of goods in the fourth quarter were 94 million euros, in 2020, it is 143 million euros, which means a 51.26% increase. Imports of goods also increased in the fourth quarter, increasing trade volume by 7.67%. Regarding the exports of goods, in 2020 compared to 2019, there was an increase of 23.85%, while in the import of goods, there was a decrease of 5.72%, which led to a decline by 2.8% in the trade volume of goods in 2020 compared to the previous year. The increase in exports in 2020 has come as a result of the export of Kosovo goods to Albania, wherein the period January-September 2020, we have an increase of 6.16% compared to the same period in 2019, an increase of 1.6% in exports to Germany, to Sweden 1.8%, and exports to the US of 3.20%.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the paper suggests that the voters evaluate political leaders for their policy choices, not just the consequences of a pandemic. They can be punished in terms of political approval when measures are accelerated in time, as we elaborated in Kosovo's case, or when there is a lack of effective blocking measures, as we elaborated in the

United States. Therefore, economic indicators endangering public health do not seem to be strong predictors of political approval rates during this crisis.

North Macedonia and Albania have been more affected by foreign trade accounts due to the crisis posed by COVID-19, compared to Kosovo, which has seen an increase in exports of goods accounts. From the above figures, we can see that the crisis presented due to the pandemic in Kosovo has mostly affected imports of goods for 2020, rather than the exports of goods for the same period. This may be because Kosovo did not apply restrictive policies regarding the movement of goods than North Macedonia and Albania and because it is not part of international organizations, the rules and principles of which become mandatory for member states. Countries with larger trade volumes are more affected by the COVID-19 crisis.

RECENSENTË:

Prof. dr. Drita M. Fazlia

Prof. dr. Metush Sulejmani

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